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References

1. S. SHIBATA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1960, **23**, 367.
2. S. SHIBATA and I. ISHIGURO, *Nagoya Kogyo Gijutsu Shikensho Hokoku*, 1962, **11**, 318.
3. S. SHIBATA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1963, **28**, 388.
4. O. NAVRÁTIL, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1966, **31**, 2492.
5. R. G. ANDERSON and G. NICKLESS, *Analyst*, 1967, **92**, 207.
6. H. DESAI and H. GANDHI, *Chim. Anal. (Paris)*, 1968, **50**, 297.
7. M. LANGOVA-HNILIČKOVA and L. SOMMER, *Folia Fac. Sci. Nat. Univ. Purkyniahao Brono.*, 1968, **9**, 2.
8. CHANG TIAO-HSU, LIN AI-LING and YANG SU-ING, *Hua Hsueh*, 1971, **1**, 111.
9. S. SHIBATA, 'Chelates in Analytical Chemistry' Edited by H. A. Flascka and A. J. Bernard (Jr) Vol. IV, Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, 1972.
10. D. BETTERIDGE and D. JOHN, *Analyst*, 1973, **98**, 390.
11. I. M. RAO and D. SATYANARAYANA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem. (In press)*.
12. I. M. RAO, D. SATYANARAYANA and UMESH AGARWALA, *Bull. Chem Soc. Japan*, 1979, **52**, 588.
13. I. M. KOLTHOFF and P. J. ELVING, 'Treatise on Analytical Chemistry' Vol VIII, Part 2, Interscience, New York, 1963, p. 57.
14. B. F. PEASE and M. B. WILLIAMS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, **31**, 1044.
15. J. S. COLEMAN, L. P. VARGA and S. H. MASTIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **9**, 1015.
16. P. JOB, *An Chim (Paris)*, 1928, **9**, 113.
17. W. LIKUSSAR and D. F. BOLTZ, *Anal. Chem.*, 1971, **43**, 1265.

Effect of Aluminium Sulfate on Potassium Release and pH of Kaolinite Type Tea Soils

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CHENARY¹ reported that aluminium is well assimilated by the calcifirgedtea plants. The productivity of tea soils are being maintained by the supply of essential nutrients like nitrogen, potassium, phosphorous etc and every year 1000 kg crop of tea removed 20 kg/ha of potassium^{2,3}. It has been found that a thirteen year old tea bush utilizes 900 kg of potash per hectare every year⁴. This laboratory study attempts to see the availability of inherent potassium, in soil as effected by application of hydrated aluminium sulfate. Where symptoms of K-deficiency are apparent on the tea

bushes top dressings ranging from 200 to 400 kg/ha of muriate or sulfate of potash are suggested according to severity of symptoms. Further the study also envisages on the pH effect of aluminium sulfate⁵.

Experimental

Air-dried soil samples of specifications given in Table 1 was made to pass through a 100-mesh B.S.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOIL USED IN THE PRESENT STUDY

Place—Jorhat (Tooklai) 26° 47' N
Depth—0-30 cm.

(A) Aggregate analysis

Grain Size	% on a dry wt. basis
>5 mm	0.44
5-2 mm	2.33
2-1 mm	1.66
1-0.5 mm	3.43
0.5-0.25 mm	6.43
Total	14.29

(B) Mechanical Analysis (Universal Pippett Method, Piper¹⁰)

Texture	Size (mm)	% on dry wt. basis
Coarse Sand	2.000	7.55
Fine Sand	0.200	44.70
Silt	0.020	40.00
Clay	0.002	7.50

(C) Nitrogen, Carbon, Potash, Phosphate content and C/N ratio and loss on ignition analysis.

	(i)	(ii)	
Total - K ₂ O	7.4 × 10 ³ ppm	% N	0.108
Available - K ₂ O	0.09 × 10 ³ ppm	% Org.C	0.976
Total - P ₂ O ₅	0.404 × 10 ³ ppm	% Loss of Ignition	3.55
Available - P ₂ O ₅	0.004 × 10 ³ ppm	C/N Ratio	9.00

sieve and then five grams of soil was taken in aspirator bottles. The outlet of the bottles were closed with pure glasswool so that only clear supernatant solution could be taken out at pleasure. The soils were then treated with varying concentration eg. 0, 21, 63, 105 and 147 mg per 5 g soil, of BDH laboratory grade aluminium sulfate Al₂(SO₄)₃. 16 H₂O. Exchange reactions were allowed to continue at room temperature (28°) for 28 hours. The supernatant solutions were then drained out and replaced with fresh solutions of aluminium sulfate as used at 28°. Again exchange reactions were allowed to continue for 24 hours in a thermostatic waterbath controlled at 44°. The same experiment was repeated at 55°.

The pH of the extracted solutions were measured in an ELICO LI IO T pH Meter. The concentration of potassium in solution was estimated by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (Beckman 1233).

Results and Discussion

It has been found in the above study that application of aluminium sulfate to the soils lead to a

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lowering in pH value of the soil solution. It is also seen from Table 2 that the rate of lowering in pH is

TABLE 2—VARIATION IN pH AND POTASH RELEASE DUE TO APPLIED ALUMINIUM SULFATE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

Temperature	28°C		44°C		55°C	
	pH	ppm K ₂ O × 10 ³	pH	ppm K ₂ O × 10 ³	pH	ppm K ₂ O × 10 ³
Al-sulfate per 5 g soil mg						
0	10.10	2.29	10.05	1.58	9.70	1.36
21	9.90	2.66	9.80	1.95	8.80	1.66
63	9.50	3.10	8.75	2.76	6.75	2.77
105	9.30	3.81	8.05	3.76	4.20	3.95
147	8.10	5.62	5.90	5.43	3.90	4.32

enhanced by a rise in temperature. Fig. 1 depicts the changes in potassium release as effected by pH at three different temperatures namely, 28°, 44° and 55°. Fig. 2 and Table 3 show that the potassium supplying power of the soils increases with more and more additions of aluminium sulfate, in other words more potassium(K⁺) ions are released from the exchange sites. Besides, with rise in temperature the rate of release is still higher. The order and molecularity of the rate processes can be determined by undertaking kinetic studies. This means that at normal temperature K⁺ which is not available in the soil solution is made available at an increased temperature and this is further favoured by application of aluminium sulfate.

The fact that aluminium sulfate application lowers the pH of soil solution confirms the findings of Hsu and Bates⁵. They found that vermiculite treated with hydroxy aluminium solutions in the

Fig. 1. Effect of Aluminium Sulphate on potassium release from tea soils at variable temperatures.

Fig. 2. Relationship between cumulative yield of Potash and Aluminium Sulphate applied.

TABLE 3—CUMULATIVE RELEASE OF POTASH WITH TEMPERATURE AT DIFFERENT CONCEN. OF AL-SULFATE TREATMENT

Al-sulfate per 5 g soil mg	Cumulative release of K ₂ O ppm × 10 ³		
	28°C	44°C	55°C
0	2.29	3.87	5.23
21	2.66	4.61	6.27
63	3.10	5.86	8.63
104	3.81	7.58	11.53
147	5.62	11.04	15.36

range of NaOH/Al=0.3 to 1.2 showed on ageing a lowering in pH value as compared to the original solution.

The mechanism of the reaction is nothing but hydrolysis of the aluminium ions. First OH-Al polymer was formed and this enters into the lattices of the clay mineral. The Al in its turn enters into exchange reaction with the K⁺ ions which get released to the soil solutions.

The process continues until the pH becomes so low that further hydrolysis of Al³⁺ is stopped. Evidently the magnitude of lowering will depend on the concentration of Al³⁺ ion in solution.

The phenomenon can also be explained by the following sets of reactions.

The reactions (1) and (2) show the hydrolysis of aluminium sulfate leading to the formation of $Al(OH)^{+3}$ which can undergo polymerisation. The reaction (3) is nothing but protonation of a water molecule which in its turn leads to the reaction (4). Brady⁶, Black⁷ are of the opinion that the Al^{+3} formed in reaction (1) can be absorbed on the surface of soil micelle and consequently lead to exchange reaction. From the kinetic standpoint it is expected that an increasing temperature would favour the forward reactions and evidently this is clear from the data in Table 2. It is expected that for each Al^{+3} ion there shall be three exchanged K^+ ion under ideal conditions.

Again a rise in temperature accelerates the rate of exchange reaction leading to more release of K^+ from the soil matrix. It is seen that at 28° the ammonium acetate exchangeable^{9,10} potassium is only 0.57×10^3 ppm whereas after treatment with 21 mg of aluminium sulfate the soil solution contained 3.66×10^3 ppm of potassium. It has been reported that mature tea leaves contain about 1.7% aluminium, so toxic effect due to application of aluminium sulfate is far more remote^{1,9}. However there must be a critical limit upto which we can apply aluminium sulfate so that it will not interfere with uptake of phosphorous by the plant.

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References

1. E. M. CHENARY, *Pl. Soil.*, 1955, **6**, 174.
2. T. EDEN, Tropical Agricultural Services, Tea, Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., 48, Grosvenor St., London W 1, 1965.
3. C. R. HARLER, *Tea Growing*, Oxford University Press, Ely House, London W 1., 1966.
4. S. K. DEY, *Two and A Bud*, 1971, 34.
5. P. H. HSU and T. F. BATES, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1964, **28**, 763.
6. NYLE C. BRADY, *The Nature and Properties of Soil*, Macmillan Publishing Co. Inc. New York, Collier Macmillan Publishers, London, 1973.
7. C. A. BLACK, *Soil-Plant Relationship*, Wiley Eastern Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1973.
8. M. L. JACKSON, *Soil Chemical Analysis*, Prentice Hall, Inc., Engelwood Cliffs, New Jersey, 1958.
9. L. J. WEBB, *Aust. J. Bot.*, 1954, **2**, 176.
10. G. S. PIPER, *Soil and Plant Analysis*, Interscience, Publishers, Inc., New York, 1950.

Synthesis of 4-[5-(4-Methyl-2-Phenylthiazolyl)]-2-Thiazolylihydrazones of Different Carbonyl Compounds

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RECENTLY, Sawhney *et al* have reported the synthesis of differently substituted bithiazolyls as potential anti-inflammatory agents¹. As many of these compounds exhibited significant anti-inflammatory activity, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some analogous compounds. So, in continuation of our work on non-steroidal anti-inflammatory and antihelintic agents²⁻⁶, we wish to report in the present communication the synthesis of 4-[5-(4-methyl-2-phenylthiazolyl)]-2-thiazolylihydrazones(I) of different carbonyl compounds with a view to testing their anti-inflammatory activity.

I were synthesised in excellent yields according to the reaction sequence outlined in Scheme 1.

Scheme—1

1. EtOH ;
2. $Br_2/CHCl_3$.
3. $\begin{matrix} R_1 \\ R_2 \end{matrix} > C = N.NH - \overset{\overset{S}{||}}{C} - NH_2 /_{R_1OH}$ & 4. NH_4OH .

1-Acetyl-1-bromoacetone reacted smoothly with phenylthioamide in ethanol to give 5-acetyl-4-methyl-2-phenylthiazole(II)⁷. 5-Bromoacetyl-4-methyl-2-phenylthiazole(III) was obtained in good yield by the bromination of II with bromine in chloroform. III on condensation with different aldehyde and ketone thiosemicarbazones⁸, which were prepared by treating the corresponding carbonyl compounds with thiosemicarbazide in presence of acetic acid, gave respective hydrobromide salts (I. HBr) of the required hydrazones(I). The corresponding free bases(I) could be easily obtained on neutralization of I. HBr with ammonia.

The structures of the final compounds as well as intermediates were confirmed by their elemental analysis and i.r. spectra. All the final compounds(I) absorbed in the region of $3400-3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH stretching) and $1620-1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH bending) did

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